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Review Article

A Brief Review on Polyherbal Extract Having Anti-Inflammatory Activity

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ABSTRACT

This review focus on polyherbal extract having Anti-inflammatory activity. This consists essential oil of poly-herb such as turmeric, peppermint, ginger. Turmeric is a rhizome of the plant *curcuma longa*, which belongs to the family Zingiberaceae. Peppermint is an aromatic perennial herb of *Mentha piperita* L which belongs to the family Lamiaceae. Ginger is a rhizome of the plant *zingiber officinale*, which belongs to the family Zingiberaceae. They exhibit anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial and antioxidant activity. For the extraction of these essential oils, methods like Steam distillation, Hydro-distillation and Solvent extraction are preferred. They are commonly used in aromatherapy, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals and food industry.

INTRODUCTION

Inflammation is the body's natural way of protecting itself when any injury or infection is affected. The inflammation caused by the involvement of immune cells and macrophages¹. Poly-herb extract having anti-inflammatory activity helps to reduce inflammation. Turmeric also known as *curcuma longa* L. exhibits anti-inflammatory activity with active compound like curcumin¹. Ginger also known as *zingiber officinale* is widely used as anti-inflammatory

agent with active compounds like gingerol and shagaol². Peppermint or *Mentha piperita* also exhibit anti-inflammatory activity³. Essential oil extracted from these poly-herb having anti-inflammatory helps in reducing inflammation in skin, joints and muscles.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

MATERIALS:

Curcuma longa (Zingiberaceae):

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Turmeric or also known as *curcuma longa* (fig.1) which belongs to the Zingiberaceae family is commonly used for anti-inflammatory activity. Mostly turmeric was cultivated in India, China and southeast countries. Main active compound in turmeric is curcumin. They were also used as spice, food coloring and food additive. Turmeric is mainly used in traditional system of medicines⁴. Turmeric consists of different properties like Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant and Antimicrobial activity. Curcumin is the major constituent of turmeric which interact with inflammation causing agents like macrophages, cytokines and this interaction will help to reduce the swelling by its Anti-inflammatory activity⁴. Essential oil extracted from rhizomes of turmeric shows Anti-inflammatory activity. This can be used in diseases like rheumatoid arthritis, osteoarthritis and in inflammatory bowel disease.

Fig.1: *Curcuma Longa*

***Zingiber officianale* (Zingiberaceae):**

Ginger or also known as *zingiber officianale* (fig.2) which belongs to the family Zingiberaceae⁵. Studies reported that ginger have Anti-inflammatory activity. Major constituents in ginger are gingerol and shagaol². Ginger is used as spice and flavoring agent. Ginger was used in medicinal system like Ayurvedic, Unani, Aromatherapy, Allopathy and household remedies. Ginger exhibits Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Antimicrobial, and several other activities⁶. Ginger mainly cultivated in India,

China, Japan and other countries. For ginger cultivation, climate should be warm and humid and soil should be well-drained. Essential oil extracted from rhizomes of ginger exhibits Anti-inflammatory activity. This can be used in diseases like osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis and in inflammatory bowel disease.

Fig.2: *Zingiber Officianale*

***Mentha piperita* L. (Lamiaceae):**

Peppermint or also known as *Mentha piperita* L. (fig.3) is belong to the family Lamiaceae⁷. Peppermint oil which extracted from the fresh leaves of plant *Mentha piperita* L. Have Anti-Inflammatory, Antibacterial, Antiviral and Antioxidant activity^{7, 14}. Peppermint cultivated on spring season in fertile soil at pH range of 6.5 to 8.0. Peppermint consists of chemical constituents like Menthol, Menthone and Cineole. This constituent gives Anti-Inflammatory activity to the drug. Mainly composed of Phenolics and Flavonoids. So, this can be used for the various treatment of diseases like Intestinal inflammation, Digestive problems, Nervous system disorders and also in Diarrhea⁷. Essential oil extracted from leaves of peppermint exhibit anti-inflammatory activity. To treat irritable bowel syndrome peppermint oil are used¹⁵. Peppermint oil also used as flavoring agent, fragrance in cosmetics, Anti-itching and cooling agent in topical pharmaceutical products.

Fig.3: *Mentha Piperita L.*

EXTRACTION METHODS:

Extraction of Turmeric oil:

Turmeric oil can be extracted from the rhizomes of turmeric plant. It can be extracted by using methods like Steam distillation, Solvent extraction, Hydro-distillation and Supercritical fluid extraction^{8,9}. Steam distillation can be done by heating turmeric with water and the steam carries volatile oil were collected, condensed and oil separated from the water⁸. Solvent extraction can be done by using solvent, such as hexane, acetone or ethanol to dissolve the oil from turmeric, then the solvent is removed and oil is collected. Supercritical fluid extraction uses carbon dioxide in a supercritical state as a solvent⁹. Hydro-distillation this method is similar to steam distillation. Instead of steam here we use water to extract the oil by submerging the turmeric into boiling water⁹.

Extraction of Ginger oil:

Ginger oil is extracted from the rhizomes of ginger plant. It can be done by using methods like Steam distillation and Solvent extraction^{8, 10}. Steam distillation done by treating ginger with water and the steam carries oil were collected, condensed and oil separated from the water¹¹. Solvent extraction done by using solvent like ethanol or hexane and solvent get removed by evaporation, then the oil is collected¹⁰.

Extraction of Peppermint oil:

Peppermint oil extracted from the fresh leaves of plant *Mentha piperita L.* Extraction can be performed by using methods like Steam distillation, Solvent extraction and Hydro-distillation^{12, 13}. Hydro-distillation can be performed by using boiling water were leaves of peppermint were submerged¹². Steam distillation was performed by treating the leaves of peppermint with water and steam carries oil were collected, condensed and oil get separated¹³.

CONCLUSION:

Polyherbal extract having Anti-inflammatory activity can be used to prepare formulations to treat inflammation in skin, joints and muscles. Extracts of turmeric, ginger and peppermint have Anti-Inflammatory activity. The extract of polyherbs support in traditional and modern medicinal system. The Extracts of both ginger and turmeric enhances the Anti-inflammatory activity, while peppermint gives Anti-itching and cooling property. So, this can be effective in the development of polyherbal formulation.

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